

**STRENGTHENING ICT INTEGRATION AT MARBEL 1 CENTRAL
ELEMENTARY SCHOOL: AN ACTION RESEARCH ON
ENHANCING INFRASTRUCTURE DEVELOPMENT
AND PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT
FOR TEACHING STAFF**

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Strengthening ICT Integration at Marbel 1 Central Elementary School: An Action Research on Enhancing Infrastructure Development and Professional Development for Teaching Staff

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Abstract

The focus of this study was to strengthen the ICT integration of teachers at Marbel 1 Central Elementary School (MICES) by enhancing infrastructure development and professional development for teaching staff. It aimed to describe the challenges of teachers in the integration of ICT into their teaching, and then after identifying those challenges, the study aimed to propose information and communication technology (ICT) plans, which are the infrastructure development and professional development for teaching staff. The participants of the study were the seventy (70) teachers at MICES. They were chosen as the permanent teachers at the said school who are implementing the ICT integration into the teaching and learning process. This study used an action research design because it is designed to address specific issues within a particular context—in this case, improving ICT infrastructure and professional development at Marbel 1 Central Elementary School (MICES). An online survey was utilized in the gathering of data needed for the study. It aimed to assess the teachers' preparedness in using information and communication technology (ICT) in the field of teaching. The findings are categorized into four areas, such as ICT skills, ICT pedagogical skills, access and utilization, and professional development. There was also an open-ended question where the participants provided their challenges and areas for improvement on the use of ICT. The proposed ICT plans are a) infrastructure development by means of installing internet connections in the different grade level areas of the school to strengthen the use of ICT in the teaching practices of the teachers, and b) professional development by means of conducting school-based training on the use and utilization of different apps, online quizzes, and different teaching strategies that are ICT-based. The study is of big help for school principals and teachers who are struggling with no internet connection in their school. The ICT plans that this study proposed served as a guide and basis for the school to install an internet connection and to conduct school-based training on the use and utilization of ICT in teaching. They may adapt the ICT plans that this study has proposed.

Keywords: *ICT, integration, infrastructure, development, professional, teaching staff*

Introduction

With the modern technology of this generation, its impact and contribution to education are immense. Because of this, teaching and learning have become easier, more effective, engaging, interactive, and enjoyable for students. Integrating ICT not only makes teaching easier and more efficient but also simplifies other tasks for teachers, such as checking test papers, creating and computing grades, preparing reports, and even developing lesson plans and teaching-learning materials. Because of this, it is essential to provide teachers with the knowledge and skills to integrate and use ICT in their teaching. By doing so, it will make teaching easier for educators and help them deliver their lessons more effectively to students, so that they can provide quality education that ensures a brighter future for the children.

At Marbel 1 Central Elementary School, it is given that the teachers are integrating or using ICT in teaching the learners, but there is then limitation in using ICT into their teaching because of the lacking of school when it comes to technology infrastructure. based on the results of the online survey they have answered, the concern and challenges that the teachers faced are the: and the lack of adequate internet connectivity and limited professional development for teachers in using ICT in teaching. These served as hindrance for them to fully integrate ICT in teaching.

This action research aimed to address those mentioned concern and challenges of teachers implementing the proposed ICT plan focusing infrastructure development and professional development for teachers. By implementing these plans, the school can provide teachers to have the means by fully using technology into their teaching practices which resulting to improving educational outcomes for learners.

This research is important because of its alignment with the 21st century learning skills by the Department of Education (DepEd), it also emphasizes the importance of ensuring that teachers in the department have adequate knowledge in using technology for teaching children. Additionally, this can serve as a reference for other schools in developing and enhancing ICT integration in their institutions.

Research Objectives

The study aimed to identify the challenges of teachers on ICT integration and then to design a proposed information and communication technology (ICT) plans for Marbel 1 Central Elementary School. Specifically, the study sought to propose the following:

1. Internet Connectivity Plan
2. Professional Development Plan

Literature Review

The ICT integration in education has been recognized globally as it is one of the effective ways of making teaching and learning process more easy, effective, and engaging. It has been proved by studies about the important role of ICT in providing quality education to learners. This review gives emphasis on the key themes that is related to infrastructure development and professional development as the main components for enhancing and strengthening ICT integration in every school particularly at MICES.

ICT Infrastructure Development in Education

Robust ICT infrastructure, including internet connectivity, hardware, and software, is essential for effective ICT integration in schools. According to Tondeur et al. (2016), the availability of adequate ICT resources significantly influences teachers' ability to incorporate technology into their teaching practices. Likewise, studies by UNESCO (2020) also stress that internet connectivity plays a crucial role in allowing access to digital educational content, online collaboration, and professional learning networks. On the other hand, most schools within developing regions have been crippled by limited connectivity, obsolete equipment, and insufficient technical support, thus making ICT programs not effectively implemented within these schools (Khan et al., 2018).

Professional Development for ICT Integration

Professional development is the basic backbone of successful ICT integration, bringing teachers the necessary skills to use technology in their work effectively. According to Guskey, professional development programs should continually be collaborative and aligned toward teachers' instructional goals and be meaningful (2002). In the context of ICT, training should, therefore, not only train technical skills but also address pedagogical strategies involving the use of technology and its enhancement of teaching and learning (Koehler & Mishra, 2009).

In the Philippines, the Department of Education has initiated its ICT Literacy Program for Teachers to equip educators in using ICT tools in teaching (DepEd, 2019). Still, research suggests that most teachers face issues such as time constraints to undergo training, limited resource access, and inadequate technical support (Villena & Besa, 2021). This is essential in promoting a culture of innovation and continuous improvement in schools.

Synergy between infrastructure and professional development

It has been observed that the integration of ICT is highly influenced by infrastructure and professional development. In fact, according to Pelgrum and Law (2003), infrastructure will not automatically lead to effective use unless it is matched with full teacher training and support. Additionally, Harris et al. (2016) point out that schools with a holistic approach to the integration of ICT—meaning they invest at the same time in both infrastructure and capacity-building—will likely have sustainable outcomes with impacts.

Local Context and Relevance

In the context of the Philippines, Basic Education Development Plan 2030 points out that ICTs would be an important leverage to enhance the quality of learning and access to learning for all. Schools such as Marbel 1 Central Elementary School must put the effort into the larger objectives by addressing gaps in infrastructures and ensuring teachers can properly use technology inside classrooms. This will, therefore, enhance ICT integration, as it aligns with both global and national trends in supporting the school's mission of providing quality education in the 21st century. This reviewed literature shows the importance of enhancing and developing both ICT infrastructure and professional development for the teachers strengthen the ICT integration in schools. By addressing these key areas, Marbel 1 Central Elementary School will be creating more conducive learning environment for an innovative teaching and learning, that is resulting to providing a quality education for learners.

Methodology

Research Design

This study is an action research design because it is designed to address specific issues within a particular context—in this case, improving ICT infrastructure and professional development at Marbel 1 Central Elementary School (MICES). An online survey was utilized in the gathering of data needed for the study. It aimed to assess the teachers' preparedness in using information and communication technology (ICT) in the field of teaching. The findings are categorized into four areas, such as ICT skills, ICT pedagogical skills, access and utilization, and professional development. There was also an open-ended question where the participants provided their challenges and areas for improvement on the use of ICT.

After the results of the survey have been analyzed, two proposed ICT plans were made: the ICT infrastructure development and professional development plans. The general objective of the study was to identify the challenges of teachers at MICES in ICT integration into their teaching and come up with ICT plans to address those challenges.

Participants

The participants of the study were the seventy (70) permanent teachers at Marbel 1 Central Elementary School (MICES) who are integrating technology into their teaching. They were all chosen to be the teachers at the school and to get the majority answers to the

survey. The teachers-participants were from different grade levels: six (6) from the kindergarten, four (4) from SNED, eleven (11) from grade 1, eight (8) from grade 2, eleven (11) from grade 3, ten (10) from grade 4, ten (10) from grade 5, and ten (10) from grade 6, for a total of 70 teachers. During the conduct of the online survey, there were only 50 teachers who were able to answer the survey.

Instrument

The survey instrument used in this study was a fully adapted survey tool from the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) created by Davis et al. (1989), Koehler & Mishra (2009), who contributed to the TPACK framework, and UNESCO (2011). The aim of this survey is to assess the teachers' preparedness in using information and communication technology (ICT) in the field of teaching. The findings are categorized into four areas, such as: ICT Skills, ICT Pedagogical Skills, Access and Utilization, and Professional Development and ICT. There is also an open-ended question where the participants provided their challenges and areas for improvement on the use of ICT.

Procedure

Permission to conduct the study was requested from the principal of Marbel 1 Central Elementary School (MICES). After the approval, coordination was done with the teacher chairman per grade level, and a message was sent to the school official Group Chat (GC) informing and asking all teachers to answer the online survey. The researchers explained to the participants what the research is all about. The standard research protocols were followed, such as ensuring their anonymity in the entire research process and the confidentiality of the answered survey. The survey was conducted over three days. The researchers thanked the teachers-participants for answering the online survey.

Data Analysis

The study used descriptive statistics like percentage analysis, where the researchers computed the percentage of responses for each level of agreement or each category, and frequency distribution, where researchers identify and present the number of respondents for each category. In analyzing the data, there was a weighted mean or mean score, such as a rating of 3.55–5.00, which is the highest score, and 1.00–3.54 is the lowest score or rating. For the open-ended questions, thematic analysis was used to identify the recurring themes like “slow internet connection” or “lack of training” as the challenges of the participants.

Results and Discussion

Proposed Plans

A. Internet Connectivity Plan

This process chart shows the implementation framework for the internet connectivity plan to address the needs and challenges of the teachers at M1CES.

Alignment of the School’s Vision-Mission-Goals with the Internet Connectivity of the Technology Plan for Internet Connectivity Goals and Key Competency Targets

<i>School Vision, Mission, and Policy</i>	<i>Goals and Key Competency Targets (Internet Connectivity and Installation Plan)</i>
<p>THE DEPED VISION We dream of Filipinos who passionately love their country and whose values and competencies enable them to realize their full potential and contribute meaningfully to building the nation. As a learner-centered public institution, the Department of Education continuously improves itself to better serve its stakeholders</p>	<p>The objectives of the Internet Connectivity plan will be the following:</p> <p>Quarter 1: Assessment and Initial Planning</p> <p>Objectives: Identify areas with and without internet. Estimate the area that requires internet wiring and setup. Identify potential internet service providers (ISPs).</p> <p>Quarter 2: Installing Internet wiring</p> <p>Objectives: Install wiring in areas without internet. Set up internet hardware and determine optimal bandwidth. Connect enough devices to meet school needs.</p> <p>Quarter 3 and 4: Optimization and Sustainability</p> <p>Objectives: Optimize bandwidth for efficient usage. Establish a long-term maintenance plan. Monitor costs and upgrade as needed.</p>
<p>THE DEPED MISSION To protect and promote the right of every Filipino to quality, equitable, culture-based, and complete basic education where: Students learn in a child-friendly, gender-sensitive, safe, and motivating environment. Teachers facilitate learning and constantly nurture every learner. Administrators and staff, as stewards of the institution, ensure an enabling and supportive environment for effective learning to happen. Family, community, and other stakeholders are actively engaged and share responsibility for developing life-long learners.</p>	
<p>DEPED POLICY ON THE USE OF TECHNOLOGY IN TEACHING Based on the Department Order No. 016, s. 2023 which is the Revised Guidelines on the Implementation of the Department of Education Computerization Program, the Department of Education issued the DCP to provide schools and DepEd offices with appropriate quality, and equitable technologies that would enhance the teaching, learning, governance, and operation processes, practices, programs and policies to meet the challenges of the modern age.</p>	

Processes Of The One (1) Year Internet Connectivity Plan

This one (1) year internet connectivity plan shows the details of the tasks to be done every year of the one-year plan. This covers the a) processes for the internet connectivity plan, b) Gantt Chart and c) the estimated cost of the plan.

A. Processes for the Internet Connectivity Plan

<i>Components</i>	<i>Quarter 1</i>	<i>Quarter 2</i>	<i>Quarter 3 And 4</i>
Assessment and Initial Planning			
1. Assessments/Survey for Teachers on the Importance of having internet connectivity			
2. School planning on the internet connectivity			
3. Sessions or open forum to be attended by the teachers and resource persons from Division and PLDT office.			
4. Identifying the Internet providers			
5. Estimating the school area for wiring			
6. Budget Planning			
Installing Internet Wiring			
7. Purchase of equipment			
8. Installing of internet wiring			
9. Connecting devices			
10. Testing and Troubleshooting			
Optimization and Sustainability			
11. Evaluating the usage and speed of the internet			
12. Securing monthly fees			
13. Establishing Maintenance team			
14. Expand and upgrade as needed			

B. Gantt Chart

This Gantt Chart shows the management of the 1-year technology plan on the sessions for the internet connectivity as to the targeted months, hours, cluster of teachers and the no. of teachers who are involved in the implementation of the plan. On the first quarter, the first session on the assessment or the conduct of the survey for teachers as to their needs of the internet connection and initial planning for the one-year internet connectivity plan will be held on the 4th day of September, and the teachers to attend the session will be the cluster 1 composed of Special Education Teacher (SET) and Kinder teachers with the total of 10 teachers. on the 2nd quarter, the second session will be held on the 4th day of October and the target teachers to attend the session will be the cluster 2 composed of the grade 1 and grade 2 teachers. While on the 3rd and 4th quarters cluster 3 and cluster 4 will be combined in attending the session that is on the 2nd day of February. The teachers to attend the session will be the grades 3-6 teachers with the total of 41 teachers.

C. Estimated Cost

Items	Quarter 1	Quarter 2	Quarter 3 And 4	Total
Assessment and Initial Planning	3,000.00 Php	4,000.00 Php	8,000.00 Php	15,000.00 Php
1. Assessment/Survey for Teachers.	(Teachers' snacks and for the speaker)	(Teachers' snacks and for the speaker)	(Teachers' snacks and for the speaker)	
2. School planning on internet connectivity	2,000.00 (honorarium and token for the resource speaker)	2,000.00 (honorarium and token for the resource speaker)	2,000.00 (honorarium and token for the resource speaker)	6,000.00 Php
3. Open forum with teachers and resource persons	N/A	N/A	N/A	
4. Identify the internet providers	N/A	N/A	N/A	
5. Estimating the school area for wiring	N/A	N/A	N/A	
Installing Internet Wiring		500 meters (6,500.00 Php)	N/A	6,500.00 Php
6. Purchase or equipment (routers, switches, modems)		5 routers (10,000.00 Php)		10,000.00 Php

7. Installing internet wiring	N/A	1,000.00 per person		5,000.00 Php
		(5,000.00 Php for 5 persons)		
8. Connecting devices	N/A	N/A	N/A	
9. Testing and troubleshooting	N/A	N/A		
Optimization and Sustainability	N/A	N/A	3,000.00 Php	3,000.00 Php
10. Evaluating usage and speed				
11. Securing monthly fees for 1 year	N/A	N/A	4 Wi-Fi connections (300 MBPS/ 2999 Php.	143,000.00 Php
12. Establishing maintenance team	N/A	N/A	N/A	
Expanding and upgrading	N/A	N/A	N/A	
Total		5,000.00 Php	22,500.00 Php	156,000.00 Php
				183,500.00 Php

This table shows the estimated cost for the internet connectivity plan within one (1) year. On the first quarter of the plan, the amount of money that will be spent of the school is Five Thousand Pesos (5,000.00), on the second quarter will be Twenty-two Thousand Five Hundred Pesos (22,500.00), and on the third and fourth quarter will be One Hundred Fifty-Six Thousand for a total of One Hundred Eighty-three Thousand Five Hundred Pesos (183,500.00) only.

Bases For The Estimated Cost

<i>Items</i>	<i>Materials Needed</i>	<i>Estimated Price</i>
Assessment/Survey for Teachers	Snacks and bond papers for 70 teachers	Session 1 (3,000.00) Session 2 (4,000.) Session 3 for cluster 3 and 4 (8,000.00)
School planning on internet connectivity	Resource Speaker	Bond paper (200.00) Honorarium (P1,000.00) Token (P500.00)
Purchase or equipment (routers, switches, modems)	Wire Routers modems	Wire (P13 per meter) Router (2,000. Per piece) Modem (C/O PLDT)
Installing internet wiring	Labor	1,000.00 per person
Monthly Fees	50 TO 100 MBPS 100 TO 300 MBPS 200 TO 600 MBPS	50 TO 100 MBPS (2,399.00) 100 TO 300 MBPS (2,999.00) 200 TO 600 MBPS (4,099.00)

Evaluation and Monitoring

The internet connectivity plan shall be going through processes; on the first day of the plan, in a session, an assessment or survey shall be given to the teachers to identify and determine their needs and concerns on the need for internet connectivity. On the second quarter, procuring, installing, connecting devices, and testing and troubleshooting shall be done. On the third and fourth quarters of the plan will focus on evaluation, maintenance, and sustainability. All these processes shall be evaluated and monitored by the school head with the assistance of the primary teachers and some teachers who have expertise in ICT skills.

A Technology Plan for Teachers’ Professional Development at MICES

Rationale

Teachers are regarded as the foundation of the educational system worldwide and can have a significant impact on a country's economic and long-term development. Every institution has distinct goals and objectives, and they cannot be met unless its children acquire outstanding educational opportunities. Teachers must expand their knowledge and abilities to keep up with the rapid changes in society. Traditional teaching methods, approaches, and strategies are impeding progress and failing to meet the demands of students, stakeholders, and the educational system. Teachers' current knowledge and abilities must be updated to overcome these obstacles. However, this is only feasible if educators are personally motivated, committed, and dedicated to learning new information and skills regarding contemporary technologies like ICT, which have been utilized in the educational system for the past several decades to enhance teachers' knowledge and abilities.

ICT has a significant influence on the educational process and on learning activities like since ICT has undoubtedly impacted teaching and learning (Teo, 2008). An additional advantage of ICT is that it can be used effectively both within and outside of the classroom to improve teacher-student contact and communication (Hammond, 1998;

Giordano (2007). ICT's explosive growth has resulted in major shifts and developments of the twenty-first century, and their integration into the educational system enhances effectiveness of instructional activities (Knezek & Christensen, 2002; Gorder, 2008; Sim and Lau (2008). However, effective ICT use in a classroom environment fosters a difficulty for administrators and teachers; as ICT cannot be used without planning intended goals for teachers (Ali, Haolader, & Muhammad, 2008). Consequently, Teachers must become ICT

literate to be competent and successful 21st-century educators, as well as proficient ICT users

The goal of Marbel I Central Elementary School's ICT Technology Plan initiative is to address issues. It focuses on how teachers may utilize ICT to enhance their professional development in the learning process. This technology plan proposal intends to help the school by providing ICT Professional Development Training specifically on ICT Based Assessment Strategies to achieve the Vision as a child-centered public school which continuously improves itself to better serve stakeholder and share responsibility for generating life-long learners.

ICT Professional Development Framework

These procedures taken by proponents to determine the ICT needs and competencies of teachers and to develop solutions to meet those needs are depicted in this flowchart for ICT Professional Development. The team will be led by the principal, the ICT coordinator or coordinators and SLAC coordinator in evaluating and organizing any desired improvements.

Alignment of the DepEd School’s Vision-Mission-Goals Statement with the ICT Professional Development Training Goals and Key Competency Targets

<i>DepEd School’s Vision-Mission-Goals</i>	<i>ICT Professional Development Program Goals and Key Competency Targets</i>
<p>Vision We dream of Filipinos who passionately love their country and whose values and competencies enable them to realize their full potential and contribute meaningfully to building the nation. As a learner-centered public institution, the Department of education continuously improves itself to better serve its stakeholders.</p>	<p>This Professional Development Program’s goal, as a learner-centered institution, is to exemplify 21st century abilities yet uphold data security and privacy. The development program will achieve the following in accordance with the objectives of the institution:</p>
<p>Mission To protect and promote the right of every Filipino to quality, equitable, culture-based, and complete basic education where: students learn in a child-friendly, gender-sensitive, safe and motivating environment. Teachers facilitate learning and constantly nurture every learner. Administrators and staff. As stewards of the institution, ensure an enabling and supportive environment for effective learning to happen. Family, community, and other stakeholders are actively engaged and share responsibility for developing life-long learners.</p>	<p>a. Empower faculty and staff with the knowledge, skills and confidence to effectively integrate technology into their teaching practices. b. Provide necessary technological resources which are beneficial for an enhanced, efficient and effective teaching-learning.</p>
<p>Goals Using technology in the classroom to enhance teaching-learning process. Empowering faculty and staff with the knowledge, skills and confidence to effectively integrate technology into their teaching practices. Provide necessary technological resources which are beneficial for an enhanced, efficient and effective teaching-learning. Giving management assistance with logistics and other administrative support for curriculum integration initiatives and programs, formative development teachers and</p>	<p>Key Competency Targets a. Showcase that you can do simple repairs and maintenance and help with software issues. b. Manage student project-based learning activities in a technology-enhanced environment to support collaboration, communication and critical thinking.</p>

staff as well as in technology infrastructure.

c. Showcase the usage of a variety of ICT technologies to enhance assessment (gamification).

Flowchart of the Needs Assessment for ICT Professional Development

The procedure to assess teachers' ICT needs and competencies, which will form the foundation of the ICT Professional Development Program, is depicted in the flowchart. It offers the guidelines that need to be adhered to both before and after assessing the teachers' proficiency. The teacher's overall objective is to demonstrate at least 90% mastery of the skills. And continuously use the knowledge gained in all teaching activities through crafting ICT-Based Assessment and sharing implications of this assessment during weekly Collaborative Expertise Period provided with minutes submitted to the SLAC Coordinator every week or become a co-facilitator in the development training

Logistics of the Training

The training includes the topics modified from the training module of Ministry of Education of Rwanda (2017).

Topics for the Trainings

<i>Topics</i>	
1	Trouble Shooting ICT problems
2	ICT Support for Assessment (LUMI Application-an offline assessment tool and Interactive Power Point)
3	ICT Support for Assessment (Gamification Apps)

Topics identified above are based on the ICT Needs and Assessment Survey that was participated by 55 out of 70 teachers. Topics that have low ratings are Trouble Shooting of ICT Problems inside the classroom earned a rating of 3.54 and ICT training on assessment-based applications earned a rating of 3.46. The school will conduct the training during the School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) Sessions to adhere with the DepEd Memorandum No. 35 series 2016 which aims to improve and support teachers' professional development based on the principle of lifelong learning and DepEd's commitment to improve practice and learners' achievement.

For grades two through six, the school must reduce the time from forty-five to thirty minutes. assuming eight subjects per day and six hours of classroom instruction for all grade levels. to be utilized during the second and fourth Friday of the month of training. Since grade 1 interactions only last for half a day, no subject will be affected. To prevent too much disruption of certain sessions, classes will

be shortened for each cluster on second and fourth Fridays of the month.

A. Gantt Chart Plot for the Whole Year Trainings

		(certificates for the speaker & participants)	(certificates for the speaker & participants)
4	Snacks	P 10, 000	P 10, 000
5	Honorarium/Token for The Key Resource Person	P 3,000.00	P 3,000.00
6	Hotel Accommodation	N/A	N/A
		(School-Based Training)	(School-Based Training)
7	Venue	School ICT Laboratory Room	School ICT Laboratory Room
	Total	P 14,500.00	P 14,500.00

Based on the consultation made with the school head, he stressed that the school's maintenance and other operational expenses (MOOE) budget cannot sustain to fully support the ICT needs of the school.

As a result, the institution's other local funds are anticipated to cover the anticipated expenses. The table above shows the overall anticipated expenses of the entire training costing to P 14,500.00 that will be generated from school's other local funds.

Evaluation

On the 3rd day of their training week, teachers will receive their final evaluation to ensure they have met the general goals of the ICT Professional Development Training. Sorted components from the ICT Needs and Competency Assessment make up the assessment. The Focal Persons will oversee organizing the documentation and developing new evaluation forms upon the completion of the program. Teachers will be monitored by mentors until they achieve the required level of mastery if they are unable to demonstrate the necessary competency.

To be eligible for a certificate of course completion with CPD Units at the completion of training, the teacher must craft an ICT-Based Assessment Output as an application of their learning during the training on topics 2&3, then take the assessment and be able to achieve a minimum of 90% on all assessments of the competencies. Teachers will be monitored by mentors until they achieve the required level of mastery if they are unable to demonstrate the necessary competency.

Mentoring

Teachers who score 90% or higher on the ICT Needs and Competency Assessment, indicating a high level of ICT proficiency, will be able to help as co-facilitators throughout the trainings.

To keep the standard, they should receive the same rating or a higher one in the yearly evaluation. In addition to becoming co-facilitators, they provide priority to ICT training possibilities. Additionally, they are responsible for mentoring other educators for just-in-time learning.

As a designated mentor and co-facilitator, the teacher must be patient and show a strong desire to improve his ICT skills. It's imperative to assess both the mentor and the mentee's competence before establishing a mentorship relationship by understanding what it entails.

The following actions must be taken by mentors for the Just-In-Time Learning Process to be successful:

Listen attentively, be a good listener about the concerns and needs of your mentee so they may feel accepted and build trust.

Aid the mentee to address the concerns and needs, reteach the skill if necessary.

Allow the mentee to demonstrate the skills alone to know if he/she learned the concept taught.

Check the appropriateness of the performance of the mentee.

Make a follow-up with the mentee.

Monitoring

Throughout the Professional Development Training process, monitoring is done to see how teachers respond to the training, to reinforce any challenges they may have had, and to track any progress or development toward the objectives. Monitoring and assessment are related in that they both focus on achieving the goals. Frequent monitoring and assessment will be useful in determining how well the program is being implemented in relation to its objectives. Strategies will also be adjusted as needed to enhance training and guarantee efficient use of time and resources

Materials

The table below shows the overall anticipated materials of the entire training

<i>Materials Needed</i>	<i>Quantity</i>	<i>Source Of Fund</i>	<i>Persons Responsible</i>
Certificates	80pcs	Local Funds (IGP, Kabugwason, etc)	Focal Persons (ICT & LAC Coordinators)
Laptops/Desktop	20 units	Personal, MOOE, Local Funds	Teachers, ICT Coordinator/s, School Head

Conclusions

The proposed ICT plans are a) infrastructure development by means of installing internet connections in the different grade level areas of the school to strengthen the use of ICT in the teaching practices of the teachers, and b) professional development by means of conducting school-based training on the use and utilization of different apps, online quizzes, and different teaching strategies that are ICT-based. The study is of big help for school principals and teachers who are struggling with no internet connection in their school. The ICT plans that this study proposed served as a guide and basis for the school to install an internet connection and to conduct school-based training on the use and utilization of ICT in teaching. They may adapt the ICT plans that this study has proposed

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